

Fitness for transport

LIVE ANIMALS ANIMAUX VIVANTS LEBENDE TIERE

Biology and needs

Livestock are transported by land (road or rail), sea and air for slaughter, to growing or fattening units, to change ownership, for breeding purposes or to attend shows or competitions.

Currently no widely agreed scientific definition of the concept of fitness for transport exists but it can be defined as the ability of an animal to cope with transport stresses, meaning that the animal has control of mental and bodily stability. Transport as an often unfamiliar and threatening procedure in an animal's life involves a series of handling and confinement situations that are clearly stressful and can lead to distress, injury or even death if the animal is not fit and if the process is not properly planned and executed. Transport is therefore a multifactorial stressor that can have a detrimental effect on health, welfare and performance but also product quality.

A number of welfare consequences have been identified as being highly relevant to the welfare during transport (**cattle, equidae, small ruminants**: handling stress, heat stress, injuries, motion stress, prolonged hunger, prolonged thirst, restriction of movement, resting problems, sensory overstimulation; **cattle, equidae**: respiratory disorders; **cattle, small ruminants**: social stress; **equidae**: gastro-enteric disorders, isolation stress, separation stress; **small ruminants**: predation stress) and only fit animals are able to cope without suffering.

Many risks to animal welfare can be mitigated by providing appropriate facilities and equipment for handling and transportation, as well as adequate training and supervision of the people operating the facilities, handling the animals and driving the vehicles. However, ensuring that only fit animals are loaded –

which can be assessed by means of animal-based measures – is one of the most important aspects in the process. Further, the animals' condition may deteriorate during transport which is why arrangements have to be made in advance to minimise the length of the journey. Such deterioration must be taken into account when assessing fitness for transport so that the animal stays fit throughout the journey.

Legal requirements

Council Regulation (EC) No 1/2005 of 22 December 2004 on the protection of animals during transport requires that no animal shall be transported unless it is fit for the intended journey. Animals that are injured, that present a physiological weakness, or a pathological process are not considered fit for transportation according to the regulation. However, animals that are only slightly injured or ill may be considered fit for transport if transportation would not cause additional suffering. In cases of doubt, advice from a veterinary practitioner shall always be sought.

In terms of accountability of assessing an animal's fitness for transport, EU legislation mentions, for example, farmers, owners, managers, but also business agents, transport companies or vehicle drivers. Thus assignment of responsibilities is not precise and therefore confusing.

An animal considered unfit for transportation shall receive appropriate veterinary treatment or, if a cure is considered unlikely, undergo emergency slaughter or killing as specified in Council Regulation (EC) No 1099/2009. Further details are also provided in the Q2E on Emergency killing of bovines and small ruminants.

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Method

Fitness for transport can be assessed by means of animal-based measures and farm recordings related to:

- Injury (e.g. severe open wound, fracture)
- Physiological weakness: any weakness of an animal which is not caused by injury or disease (e.g. poor body condition, inability to move independently without pain, females past 90 % of the expected gestation period)
- Pathological process: any condition caused by injury, disease or post-surgical complications (e.g. swelling, prolapse, impaired vision, mastitis)

Further details on the assessment are provided in the respective **Indicator factsheets**:

- '**Fitness for transport of bovine animals**',
- '**Fitness for transport of equine animals**', and
- '**Fitness for transport of small ruminants**'.

Focus areas for inspection

Before loading, many of the common problems can be identified and remedied. As a prerequisite to maintain welfare throughout transportation, requirements on facilities and equipment (e.g. floor space, headroom, ventilation, drinking devices) shall be appropriate for the category and age of animal being carried. Further, sufficient feed and bedding shall be carried. Animal-based measures may be used to assess the animal's fitness for transport, related to:

- Injury
- Physiological weakness
- Pathological process

Figure 1: Emaciated animals might not endure strains of transportation without undue suffering. © BOKU/SCHENKENFELDER, Josef

Figure 2: Severely overgrown claws might cause pain in animals when walking, present a high risk of injury and make it difficult to maintain balance during transport. © BOKU/SCHENKENFELDER, Josef

Figure 3: New-born as well as periparturient animals are considered unfit for transport due to physiological weakness. © INRAE/NORMANT, Sophie

Figure 4: Emaciated horse with deformity in thoracic limbs is unfit for transport. © iStock/AFHUNTA

Legal requirements

Council Regulation (EC) No 1/2005 of 22 December 2004 on the protection of animals during transport and related operations.

“‘long journey’ means a journey that exceeds 8 hours, starting from when the first animal of the consignment is moved;”

(Article 2, (m))

“‘transporter’ means any natural or legal person transporting animals on his own account, or for the account of a third party;”

(Article 2, (x))

“No person shall transport animals or cause animals to be transported in a way likely to cause injury or undue suffering to them.”

(Article 3)

“Transporters shall transport animals in accordance with the technical rules set out in Annex I.”

(Article 6, 3.)

“No animal shall be transported unless it is fit for the intended journey, and all animals shall be transported in conditions guaranteed not to cause them injury or unnecessary suffering.”

(Annex I, Chapter I, 1.)

“Animals that are injured or that present physiological weaknesses or pathological processes shall not be considered fit for transport and in particular if: (a) they are unable to move independently without pain or to walk unassisted; (b) they present a severe open wound, or prolapse; (c) they are pregnant females for whom 90 % or more of the expected gestation period has already passed, or females who have given birth in the previous week; (d) they are new-born mammals in which the navel has not completely healed; (e) they are [...] lambs of less than one week and calves of less than ten days of age, unless they are transported less than 100 km;”

(Annex I, Chapter I, 2.)

“However, sick or injured animals may be considered fit for transport if they are: (a) slightly injured or ill and transport would not cause additional suffering; in cases of doubt, veterinary advice shall be sought; (b) transported for the purposes of Council Directive 86/609/EEC if the illness or injury is part of a research programme; (c) transported under veterinary supervision for or following veterinary treatment or diagnosis. However, such transport shall be permitted only where no unnecessary suffering or ill treatment is caused to the animals concerned; (d) animals that have been submitted to veterinary procedures in relation to farming practices such as dehorning or castration, provided that wounds have completely healed.”

(Annex I, Chapter I, 3.)

“When animals fall ill or are injured during transport, they shall be separated from the others and receive first-aid treatment as soon as possible. They shall be given appropriate veterinary treatment and if necessary undergo emergency slaughter or killing in a way which does not cause them any unnecessary suffering.”

(Annex I, Chapter I, 4.)

“Lactating females of bovine, ovine and caprine species not accompanied by their offspring shall be milked at intervals of not more than 12 hours.”

(Annex I, Chapter I, 6.)

“Requirements of paragraphs 2(c) and 2(d) do not apply for registered Equidae if the purpose of the journeys is to improve the health and welfare conditions of birth, or for newly born foals with their registered mares, provided that in both cases the animals are permanently accompanied by an attendant, dedicated to them during the journey.”

(Annex I, Chapter I, 7.)

“Except if accompanied by their mother, long journeys are only permitted for domestic Equidae and domestic animals of bovine and porcine species if: [...]

— calves are older than fourteen days, [...].”

(Annex I, Chapter VI, 1.9)

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